

MICROSTRUCTURES OF CARBONS AND C/C COMPOSITES SiC-COATED BY CONVERSION METHOD.

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ABSTRACT

As an oxidation protection system for C/C composites, SiC coating by conversion method(conv-SiC layer) is very important. In order to obtain clear understandings of SiC conversion mechanisms, microstructure of the conv-SiC layers on carbon substrates was inspected and the microstructural evolution process was discussed from a thermodynamical view point. As a conclusion, a dominant transportation mechanism of SiO and CO during SiC conversion is assessed to be gaseous diffusion through micropores in the growing conv-SiC region instead of solid state diffusion. A Precise microstructural analysis of the conv-SiC layer suggested its excellent adhesion characteristics with the substrates. As an important feature, a preferential growth of the conv-SiC layer on (002) plane of the pyrolytic graphite substrate was emphasized. Young's modulus of the conv-SiC, estimated from the SiC-converted isotropic graphite, was about 130 GPa owing to its porous structure with many micropores.

KEY WORDS: SiC, C/C composite, carbon material, microstructure, SiC conversion, TEM, SiO, oxidation protection, pyrolytic graphite, SiC layer, Young's modulus, elastic property.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the twenty-first century, space plane or super- or hyper-sonic transports will take us far away or to the space more rapidly than achievable at present. Those transports require C/C composites to stand as a excellent structural material in oxidation environment at 2000°C or the above. Although there have been many efforts for oxidation protection systems, their achievements are far from those required. C/C composites with SiC coating can survive under oxidation environment at about 1700°C for a short period. Additional overcoatings on the SiC coating have been studied to survive C/C composite as high as 2000°C. SiC layer by conversion method (conv-SiC layer) is one of the most suitable coatings to have good adhesion with substrates such as C/C composites. In general, SiC layer by chemical vapor deposition method (CVD-SiC layer) is over laid on the conv-SiC layer. Therefore, the conv-SiC layer is a very important oxidation protection system for C/C composites. As far as the conv-SiC layer is concerned, fabrication methods and characteristics of oxidation have been reported to some extent^(1,2), but only a few reports have touched microstructural issues⁽³⁾. In R&D of the overcoating/multicoating up to 2000°C and improvement of endurance against oxidation, good adhesion characteristics between conv-SiC layer and C/C composite would be required with the highest priority. The objective of this work is to establish fundamental understandings on the mechanism of SiC conversion on carbon and to obtain insights of optimizing performance of the SiC coating. This paper provides microstructural information by means of transmission electron microscopy (TEM) together with considerations from a thermodynamical view point.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1. Materials

Isotropic graphite (EG38-SH, Nippon Carbon Co. Ltd.,Japan) and pyrolytic graphite (PYRO-SSG, Pfizer Inc.,USA) were selected as graphite substrates. The isotropic graphite was made of coke powder and pitch binder through processes of carbonization, graphitization and purification. The pyrolytic graphite was also selected as an anisotropic material. As C/C composite substrates, two types of reinforcement, such as PAN-type and Pitch-type fibers, were selected and were used in the shape of flat woven fabrics.

2.2. SiC conversion treatment

Surfaces of carbon substrates were coated with SiC by a conversion method^(1,2). As shown in Fig. 1, the carbon substrates were set in a graphite crucible filled with powder mixture, and was heated at 1800°C for 1hr. in Ar atmosphere. The powder mixture consists of SiC, Si and Al₂O₃. The surfaces of carbon substrates are converted to SiC through the following reaction with SiO gas provided from the powder mixture.

Details of the reaction are mentioned in the section 4.1.

2.3. Characterization

As received and SiC-converted carbon substrates were analyzed by X-ray diffraction(XD) analysis, scanning electron microscopy(SEM), and electron probe micro analysis(EPMA). Specimens for TEM were prepared using conventional methods of sectioning, mechanical thinning, and ion milling with 2.5keV Ar ions. Young's modulus was measured by one of the authors and his colleague⁽⁴⁾ by means of lateral vibration method⁽⁵⁾ for as-received and SiC-converted isotropic graphite substrates, using specimens with the size of 80 mm x 5 mm x 1 mm.

Fig.1 Sample setting for SiC conversion.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Isotropic graphite

The XD pattern of SiC-converted isotropic graphite, as shown in Fig.2, indicates that the conv-SiC layer consists of α -SiC and a small amount of residual graphite. The thickness of conv-SiC layer from the surface of the substrate is 200 μ m in average, as shown in Fig.3. And the fraction

Fig.2 X-ray diffraction pattern of SiC-converted isotropic graphite(EG-38SH).

Fig.3 Conv-SiC layer on isotropic graphite (EG-38SH).

of SiC decreases gradually as position deepens from the surface. A representing microstructure in the depth of $100\ \mu\text{m}$ from the surface is shown in Fig.4, where thickness of conv-SiC covering surfaces of the pores is about $2\ \mu\text{m}$.

For TEM observation of conv-SiC layer, specimens were sectioned parallel to its surface of the substrate. The graphite region was classified into two types of microstructure, such as an onion like structure and an unidirectionally oriented structure. On the other hand, the conv-SiC shows only one type of microstructure, which consists of fine SiC grains and many micropores with the size of about $200\ \text{nm}$, as shown in Fig.5. Most of the micropores included in the conv-SiC were not artificially formed during specimen preparation for TEM by dropping off and preferential sputtering of SiC grains. The precise and microscopic observation of interface between SiC and graphite clearly indicated that there were neither extreme crystal growth nor formation of interfacial layers, as shown in Fig.6.

Fig.4 Microstructure of conv-SiC layer (about $100\ \mu\text{m}$ in depth).

Fig.5 TEM image of conv-SiC with micropores.

Fig.6 Interfacial microstructure between conv-SiC and graphite (EG-38SH).

Young's modulus of the as-received and SiC-converted specimens at 20°C were 7.0GPa and 35.2GPa, respectively⁽⁴⁾. And SiC distribution measured by EPMA in SiC-converted substrate is shown in Fig.7. With these data, Young's modulus of conv-SiC was estimated to be about 130GPa, which is 18 times larger than that of isotropic graphite. But this is still lower than expected from the data of sintered SiC, where Young's modulus is about 450GPa⁽⁶⁾.

Fig.7 SiC distribution of the SiC-converted isotropic graphite for lateral vibration method.

3.2. Pyrolytic graphite

In case of isotropic graphite, entire surface was uniformly converted into SiC. But, of the pyrolytic graphite, only the surface parallel to (002)plane of graphite was preferentially converted. As shown in Fig.8, in the XD pattern obtained from the surface parallel to (002)plane, peaks of SiC could be detected clearly, but that from the surface perpendicular to (002)plane, only small peaks of SiC could be detected. Even in the case of the surface parallel to (002)plane, conv-SiC layer was much thinner than that of the isotropic graphite, as shown in Fig.9. Because of the thin

Fig.8 X-ray diffraction patterns of SiC-converted pyrolytic graphite(PYRO-SSG).

Fig.9 Conv-SiC layer on pyrolytic graphite(PYRO-SSG).

Fig.10 SEM image of SiC-converted C/C composite with pitch-type carbon fibers.

Fig.11 SEM image of SiC-converted C/C composite with PAN-type carbon fibers.

conv-SiC layer, cross section specimens of the surface parallel to (002) were prepared for TEM observation. However the sputter rate of SiC is much higher than the graphite surface perpendicular to (002) plane, the specimens were not satisfactory for precise TEM inspection.

3.3. C/C composites

In case of C/C composites, entire faces were converted to SiC, which was thinner than that of the isotropic graphite. Fig.10 shows conv-SiC layer of C/C composite with pitch-type carbon fibers, some of which were converted with large carbon cores still remaining in the center. However, in C/C composite with PAN-type carbon fibers, as shown in Fig.11, most of SiC-converted carbon fibers have no carbon cores. Those were mainly due to the difference of structure of carbon fibers between PAN-type and Pitch-type such as diameter, density, orientation of graphite crystals, and also the difference of the porosity characteristics in the substrates.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. SiC conversion

As a result of thermodynamical analysis, SiC conversion process in this experiment is modeled consisting of a series of reactions shown in Fig. 12. The model is explained as follows. In the carbon substrate, conv-SiC is formed through a reaction between C of the substrate and SiO gas

Fig.12 A result of thermodynamical consideration for SiC conversion.

Fig.13. Gaseous diffusion of SiO gas through pores reacting at pore surface.

provided from powder mixture which is the reaction A in Fig.12. And at the same time CO gas is produced. SiO gas is mainly produced through a reaction between Si in the powder mixture and CO gas from the substrate, which is the reaction B in Fig.12. And, at the early stage of SiC conversion without CO gas, SiO gas is provided by a reaction between Al_2O_3 and Si in powder mixture, which is the reaction C in Fig.12. The reaction C stops at the equilibrium pressure of SiO.

Fig.13 shows that the SiO gas penetrates the substrate through its pores during SiC conversion, reacting at pore surface. Therefore, the surfaces of pores are covered with conv-SiC as shown in Fig.4. And, partial pressure of the SiO gas is decreasing gradually with the depth from surface of substrate, since SiO gas is consumed by the reaction A, passing through the pores. Also, the partial pressure of SiO gas is one of the driving forces of the reaction A. Then, SiC was gradually decreasing with the depth as shown in Fig.3. Since the pyrolytic graphite and the C/C composites are not so much penetrable for SiO gas as the isotropic graphite, their conv-SiC layers are much thinner than that of the isotropic graphite. Penetration of the SiO gas is affected by porosity characteristics of substrates. Then, SiC distribution of conv-SiC layer may be controlled by the porosity characteristics of substrate.

As for the reaction A at the surface of the pores, SiO gas cannot directly charges C of the substrate since surfaces of the pores are covered with conv-SiC. Then, the reaction A involves transportation of Si and C species through conv-SiC region. In other words, thickness of conv-

Fig.14 Transportation systems of Si and C species through conv-SiC region.

SiC is increasing with the transportation, which is that Si species moves from the surface of conv-SiC region to the SiC/C interface and C species moves from the SiC/C interface to the surface of SiC region. The transportations of Si and C species are considered using models shown in Fig.14 as follows. If the SiC region is completely gastight, Si and C atoms must be diffused in solid state. But, assuming that SiC region was formed by solid state diffusion system at 1800°C for 1 hr with a diffusion coefficient of SiC; about $1 \times 10^{-15} \text{cm}^2/\text{s}$ ⁽⁷⁾, the thickness of SiC would be far below a few μm , which was observed in Fig.4. As a result of TEM observation, SiC region had many micropores with the size of about 200nm. This size is wide enough so that CO gas and SiO gas can move. And volume fraction of the micropores are roughly large enough to form the SiC region of such a thickness. Therefore, gaseous diffusion through micropores is derived as a potential transportation system of Si and C in SiC.

From the results of XD analysis and SEM observation of the SiC-converted pyrolytic graphite, [002]direction of the graphite crystal is estimated to be a preferential direction for SiC conversion. The issue about the preferential orientation for the reaction must be discussed further after improving the preparation technique of TEM specimens, and trying to use a single crystal of graphite as a substrate for SiC conversion.

4.2. Adhesion characteristics

In this work, relations between adhesion characteristics and microstructures of conv-SiC layer were tried to point out. The following three results are important for the adhesion characteristics.

(1) Interface of conv-SiC layer was not so clear as that of CVD-SiC layer.

So, interfacial dedonding may be hardly induced. And also, the thermal stress concentration on the interface by the difference of thermal expansion coefficients may be reduced. Especially, in the SiC-converted isotropic graphite, conv-SiC layer is gradually decreasing fraction of SiC with the depth from the surface, and is a kind of SiC/C functionally gradient materials⁽⁸⁾.

(2) Conv-SiC regions had many micropores.

The thermal stress in conv-SiC layer may be reduce. Due to the micropores in conv-SiC, Young's modulus of conv-SiC may decrease. With experimental data, Young's modulus of conv-SiC was estimated and it was lower value of about 130GPa than that of sintered SiC. Also, micropores are expected to arrest microcrack propagation.

(3) At the interface between SiC region and graphite region, neither extreme crystal growth nor interfacial layers were detected.

Extreme crystal growth and interfacial layers often degrade adhesion of interface. None of such a microstructural changes are expected to appear below the conversion process temperature. So SiC/C interfaces keep excellent adhesion at least below the heated temperature during some period.

Therefore, those results are suggesting excellent adhesion characteristics of conv-SiC layer. And the adhesion characteristics may be improved by optimizing SiC distribution in the conv-SiC layer.

5. SUMMARY

In order to obtain clear understandings of SiC conversion mechanisms, microstructure of the conv-SiC layers on carbon substrates were inspected and the microstructural evolution process was discussed from a thermodynamical view point. Also elastic properties of the SiC-converted isotropic graphite were evaluated.

(1) A dominant transportation mechanism of SiO and CO during SiC conversion is assessed to be gaseous diffusion through micropores in the growing conv-SiC region instead of solid state diffusion.

- (2) A thermodynamical model to produce SiO gas during SiC conversion using powder mixture of SiC, Si and Al₂O₃ is proposed.
- (3) Excellent adhesion characteristics with the substrate are suggested by a precise microstructural analysis of the conv-SiC layer, which is represented by the following microstructures.
 - (a) Not clear interface between conv-SiC layer and substrate
 - (b) Many micropores in conv-SiC region
 - (c) Neither extreme crystal growth nor interfacial layers at interface between conv-SiC and graphite region in microscopic area.
- (4) As an important feature, a preferential growth of the conv-SiC layer on (002) plane of the pyrolytic graphite substrate is emphasized.
- (5) Young's modulus of the conv-SiC, estimated from the SiC-converted isotropic graphite, is about 130 GPa owing to its porous structure with many micropores.

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PULTRUSION

